

A STUDY OF THE QUALITY OF COMPLEX PARTS MADE USING THE MOULDLESS VARTM METHOD

C. Polowick¹, P. V. Straznický¹, J. Laliberté^{1*}

¹ Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Carleton University, Ottawa, Canada

* Corresponding author (jlaliber@mae.carleton.ca)

Keywords: *VARTM, liquid composite moulding, fiber volume fraction, compaction*

1 Introduction

Composite manufacturing research at Carleton University has focused on the development of an improved Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Moulding (VARTM) procedure to produce high quality, repeatable parts at a much lower cost than autoclave processes. Procedures developed at Carleton have been used to manufacture a low-cost composite airframe for the GeoSurv II Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV).

This paper describes an experimental method used to characterize and mitigate common manufacturing defects found in components that have been manufactured at Carleton. Specifically, an investigation is performed into the cause of corner defects and poor preform compaction when manufacturing complex three-dimensional shapes.

A novel bagging technique was developed to reduce the occurrence of corner defects, and the effects of bagging technique, corner type, and corner radius on corner thickness variation and the presence of a defect are presented.

2 Carleton University composite manufacturing

Researchers in the Low-Cost Composite (LCC) group at Carleton have been mandated to develop inexpensive composite manufacturing techniques tailored to the requirements of the GeoSurv II UAV. The following section describes the mouldless VARTM process in detail, as well as common defects that have occurred when manufacturing GeoSurv II components.

2.1 The GeoSurv II UAV

A UAV called the GeoSurv II is being developed at Carleton in collaboration with Sander Geophysics Limited (SGL) to perform mineral exploration surveys using an airborne magnetometer system. The GeoSurv II is a proof-of-concept model and testing platform designed to demonstrate that geo-magnetic surveys can be done by a UAV at lower

cost than manned aerial surveys, without putting a human pilot at risk. The GeoSurv II airframe is made from carbon fibre reinforced composites to reduce magnetic signature and decrease weight, and most components have been manufactured in-house. A diagram of the GeoSurv II UAV is shown in Fig. 1. The wings, fairings, and tail booms of the GeoSurv II have been manufactured using the VARTM process. Mouldless VARTM has been used to manufacture the fuselage, and will be used to manufacture the empennage in 2013.

2.2 Carleton mouldless VARTM

In the mouldless VARTM process, complex three-dimensional sandwich structures are made in a single infusion by using the core material as a mould during manufacturing [1,2]. Dry fabric is wrapped around the core material, which has been machined to the final shape of the part. Then, the preform is surrounded with a vacuum bag which is used to compact the fibres. The vacuum pressure is used to pull resin into the part through a series of inlets. As the part is cured, the rigid core holds the preform in its final shape. After cure, the rigid foam core remains in the part to form a sandwich structure. A diagram of the Mouldless VARTM process is shown in Fig. 2.

Mouldless VARTM has several distinct advantages for low cost composite manufacturing: large complex parts can be made to near net shape in a single step, and the foam core significantly increases the strength and stiffness of the final part without adding much weight. Furthermore, the foam core is more machinable than most mould making material, so low production run components can be made for low machining cost and time [1].

There are several disadvantages to the mouldless VARTM process. Because the vacuum bag completely encloses the preform, a high-quality surface finish comparable to that of female mould parts cannot be produced. A second disadvantage is that under vacuum pressure, the foam core does not always have the stiffness to maintain the desired

shape, and parts can sometimes cure in a deformed shape unless the core is supported [1,2]. A third disadvantage of the mouldless VARTM process is that when infusing complex parts, the vacuum bag is not able to fully fill tight corners, leading to resin-rich areas and void accumulation caused by poor compaction. This type of defect is investigated in detail in this paper.

2.3 Defects found in part corners

Corner defects of the type described in Section 2.1 have commonly been found by LCC researchers in parts with complex geometries, specifically those containing inside corners [2]. An example of this type of defect, shown in Fig. 3, was found on an inside corner in the GeoSurv II fuselage.

These corner defects are characterized by a local increase in preform thickness, as well as the presence of voids and excess resin. Three modes of corner defect formation are listed below:

1. **Bag tension:** As the preform is compacted by the vacuum pressure, the volume inside the vacuum bag is reduced. Inside corner features require the bag to stretch to fill the compacted shape. When the bag is not able to fully stretch into these corners, it cannot apply compaction pressure to the preform. This is shown in Fig. 4.
2. **Preform tension:** Another possible cause of poor corner compaction was proposed by Flynn, who described how tension in the preform can cause the fibres to not be properly compacted against an inside corner edge in RTM infusions [3]. The loss of compaction pressure in part corners due to tension in the bag or preform is called bridging, and can lead to resin rich areas [4] as well as race-tracking during the infusion process [5]. This mode is shown in Fig. 5.
3. **Fibre wrinkling:** A third cause of variability in part corners has been observed in manufacturing trials performed at Carleton; folds tended to develop when the preform was forced around a corner, and these folds would occasionally cause local corner thickness variations. This is shown in Fig. 6.

Although preform tension and fibre wrinkling contribute to corner defects, these modes can be mitigated through proper care when laying up the fabric. This experimental study focuses on the first mode of corner defect formation as this issue is not as straightforward to mitigate, and results from bag-fabric interactions.

3 Compaction of preform

The following section describes a method used to predict an ideal "flat-plate" laminate thickness and fibre volume fraction as a function of compaction pressure. A theoretical prediction of pressure losses due to bag tension is then developed. Compaction pressure losses due to corners were measured through experiment. The experimental measurements are compared to the pressure loss theory.

3.1 Compaction of flat-plate lamina

In order to achieve a high fibre volume fraction and a low final part weight, vacuum pressure is applied to the preform. The vacuum pressure compacts the fabric, decreasing the resin volume between the fibres. The compaction pressure applied to the preform can be determined using Eqn. 1 [6-8]:

$$P_{atm} = P_{comp} + P_{resin} \quad (1)$$

where P_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure, P_{comp} is the compaction pressure applied to the preform by the vacuum bag, and P_{resin} is the pressure of the resin.

The fiber volume fraction of a composite can be predicted from the compaction pressure by using Eqn. 2 [6-8]:

$$v_f = AP_{comp}^B \quad (2)$$

Where v_f is fiber volume fraction, and A and B are determined experimentally. The part thickness is related to fiber volume fraction with the following expression [1]:

$$t = \frac{N \cdot FAW}{v_f \rho_f} \quad (3)$$

Where N is number of layers, FAW is fiber area weight, ρ_f is the fiber density, and t is thickness.

3.2 Loss of compaction pressure in part corners

The thickness of lamina produced using the VARTM procedure is limited by the atmospheric pressure, but if bag tension causes a decrease in compaction pressure, the thickness of the part in the vicinity of the corner will increase, possibly leading to void formation and resin-rich areas. This phenomenon is illustrated in Fig. 7.

Using Fig. 7, the following equation for corner compaction pressure can be derived by applying sum of forces to the vacuum bag:

$$\sum F_y = 0 = C - P + 2T \sin(45^\circ) \quad (4)$$

where F_y is the force in the y direction, C is the total compaction force applied to the bag by the preform, P is the total force due to the atmospheric pressure applied to the bag, and T is the bag tension. The equations for C , P , and T are given below:

$$C = P_{comp}A' \quad (5)$$

$$P = P_{atm}A' \quad (6)$$

$$T = t_{bag}E_{bag}L \left(\frac{t_o - t_f}{R - t_f} \right) \quad (7)$$

where P_{comp} can be determined from Eqns. 2 and 3, t_o and t_f are shown in Fig. 7, R is the outer radius of the preform, L is the width of the specimen, and t_{bag} and E_{bag} are the thickness and elastic modulus of the bagging material, respectively.

A' is defined as the component of area perpendicular to the y direction, and can be determined using Eqn. 8.

$$A' = 2L(R - t_f) \sin(45^\circ) \quad (8)$$

When Eqn. 4 was solved for a 2-ply layup of woven carbon fibre, it was predicted that the compaction pressure would drop to 36 kPa in the corners, from 93 kPa in the flat section.

3.3 Measurement of corner compaction pressure

Experiments were performed to quantify compaction pressure in complex three-dimensional structures during the infusion of the third GeoSurv II fuselage. The experimentally measured pressure is compared to the theoretical value in the following section.

To measure compaction pressure, nine Force Sensing Resistors (FSRs) were mounted between the vacuum bag and the preform at various distances from inside and outside corners, as well as in flat sections.

3.3.1 FSR data acquisition

Interlink FSR400 FSRs were used to measure compaction pressure [11]. The resistance across an FSR400 sensor is related to the force applied to the sensor head. By calibrating each sensor to determine the relationship between applied pressure and resistance, the FSRs can be used to measure force.

Each FSR was connected to an Arduino Uno through a voltage divider, which converts the variable FSR resistance to a voltage. The Uno read the voltage output of the voltage divider as a value between 0 and 1024, and transmitted this value to a laptop which stored the data.

3.3.2 FSR calibration

To calibrate the FSRs, known weights were used to apply a pressure to the sensor face, and the resulting relationship between applied pressure and sensor reading was used to develop an empirical calibration curve, allowing the pressure applied to the sensor face to be determined from the sensor reading.

Pressure measurements were taken from the FSRs as vacuum pressure was drawn prior to the infusion. The GeoSurv II fuselage is shown in Fig. 8 surrounded by a custom silicone vacuum bag and instrumented with the FSRs. The locations of the FSRs on the fuselage are shown in Fig. 9. Six out of the nine sensors failed when vacuum pressure was drawn, but three sensors remained functional. These sensors were located in an inside corner center, 10 mm from the center of that corner, and in a flat section, respectively. The sensor output as vacuum pressure was drawn is shown in Fig. 10. In the flat section, the maximum recorded compaction pressure was 92.9 kPa, which was slightly less than the vacuum pressure of 96.0 kPa measured by a vacuum gauge. However, in the center of the corner, the measured compaction pressure was 29.4 kPa. These effects were still noticeable 10 mm from the corner center, as the compaction pressure in this location was only 76.4 as measured by the FSR.

The results of this experiment show that a loss of compaction pressure is experienced in inside corners of parts made using VARTM. The pressure measured in the fuselage corner agrees with the experimentally predicted pressure of 36 kPa, suggesting that the bag tension is an important factor in corner part defect formation.

4 Corner test part experiments

The following section describes a series of experiments used to quantify the detrimental effects of compaction pressure loss on part quality.

In order to quantify the quality of three-dimensional parts, 90° L-channel coupons were manufactured using the VARTM method. The dimensions of the specimens are shown in Fig 11. The effects of the

following three parameters on corner thickness, and the presence of a void were examined through experiment:

- **Corner radius:** The radius of the part corner could affect the defects present within that corner. Corner radii of 1.6 mm, 3.2 mm, 6.4 mm, and 12.7 mm were tested to determine the effects of corner radius on manufacturing defects.
- **Inside or outside corner:** Whether the preform was located on the inner or outer surface of the corner mould potentially affect the presence of manufacturing defects. Coupons were manufactured with both inside and outside corners to examine this effect.
- **Bagging method:** Interactions between the vacuum bag and preform could potentially cause defects within corner parts. To investigate the effects of bagging technique a silicone bag, which replicates the method currently used by the LCC group; and a high-elongation Stretchlon bag, with silicone pressure enhancers in the corners were tested.

These test series were used to determine the effects of bagging method, corner type, and corner radius on part tolerances, void content, and strength. Parts made using both female and male moulds (inside and outside corners, respectively) were tested to eliminate the effects of fibre wrinkling on thickness measurements; outside corners will wrinkle, but will not experience losses in compaction. Therefore, the effects of compaction pressure loss could be isolated by comparing inside corner measurements to those taken on the corresponding outside corner.

4.1 Bagging technique

The following section describes the custom silicone bagging technique currently used by LCC researchers, as well as a novel bagging technique that has been developed to reduce the formation of corner defects.

4.1.1 Custom silicone bag

The reusable custom silicone bagging technique was developed as an alternative to one-time use vacuum bags and was designed to allow complex three-dimensional shapes to be manufactured with less variability and defects. Because each bag is custom made, it will be able to conform to details within the part with a high degree of accuracy. The disadvantage of using this method is that fabricating custom silicone bags is a time-consuming process, with expensive consumables [2].

4.1.2 Stretchlon bag with pressure enhancers

A method for bagging complex parts was developed using Stretchlon vacuum bagging material instead of the custom silicone bag. Stretchlon bag is made from a thermoplastic polyester elastomer from Hytrel [9,10], and is designed to be extremely flexible, with a 600% elongation before rupture [12]. The high elongation will allow the Stretchlon bag to conform to complex geometries, without the use of a custom bag. In the new method, pressure enhancers were used in part corners to relieve any tension that may develop in the bag and cause defects associated with bag tension due to preform compaction (shown in Fig. 4). Furthermore, these pressure enhancers will act as caul plates, ensuring a smooth, uniform finish on the part corners. The goal of this method was to eliminate some of the defects found when using the silicone bagging technique, but with much less preparation time and cost. The placement of pressure enhancers in the layup is shown in Fig. 12.

4.2 Layup

When selecting the fibre layup for the corner test parts, the following two requirements were considered:

1. The test layup must be representative of what will be used on components that will be constructed for the GeoSurv II. The following three GeoSurv II components were considered by the LCC group:
 - a. The GeoSurv II fuselage was constructed out of 1-8 plies of woven carbon fibre, the majority being 1-3 plies. These plies contained balanced combinations of $(0^\circ, 90^\circ)$ and $(45^\circ, -45^\circ)$ plies.
 - b. The GeoSurv II hatch covers were constructed from 2 plies of woven carbon fibre with the following ply orientation: $[(0^\circ, 90^\circ), (45^\circ, -45^\circ)]$.
 - c. The GeoSurv II empennage will be constructed from 1-3 plies of woven carbon fibre.
2. The test layup must be thick enough that the effect of preform compaction on bag tension will be apparent; thin preforms will not display local thickness variations as prominently as thicker preforms.

A three-ply layup of 8 harness satin BGF 94107 was selected with a $[(0^\circ, 90^\circ), (45^\circ, -45^\circ), (90^\circ, 0^\circ)]$ orientation. This layup is representative of layups

that have been used in the fuselage and hatch covers, as well what will likely be used on the empennage. Furthermore, it is thick enough that any thickness variations in corners will be apparent.

4.3 Manufacturing of corner test parts

Three sets of corner test parts were manufactured for each bagging technique, for a total of 48 specimens. The corner test parts were then cut to the final shape with the dimensions shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 13 shows an example of the layup and bagging method used when manufacturing the Stretchlon test parts. The yellow tacky tape used to seal the mould can be seen around the edges of this layup, and was placed between the bag and the mould. In the silicone bag layup, however, this tacky tape was placed on top of the bag and sealed against the mould face to replicate the method used on the GeoSurv II fuselage.

5 Results

The following section describes the measurement of part thickness and corner void defects, and presents the data for the corner test parts.

5.1 Presentation of data

When presenting the data gathered in the corner test experiments, the specimens were grouped in the following manner:

- By corner type and bagging method. Each group contained 12 specimens.
- By corner radius. Each group contained 12 specimens.

The average and standard deviation of thickness variation for the specimens in each of these groups is presented in the following three sections. The error bars on each plot show one standard deviation.

5.2 Thickness variability in corner test parts

The theoretical thickness of the layup under atmospheric pressure was determined to be 1.2 mm using Eqn. 1 and Eqn. 2. The thickness of the corner test parts was measured at various locations, and compared to this experimental value. The effects of bagging type, corner type, and corner radius on thickness are presented below.

5.2.1 Measurement method

Digital calipers were used to take measurements at various distances from the mid- point of the corner

of each part. Six measurements were taken in the flat sections of each specimen, far away from the corners. In the specimens with a 1.6 mm corner, one thickness measurement was taken at the midpoint of each corner due to the corner's small size. In every other specimen, four thickness measurements were taken at fixed locations around the part corner.

5.2.2 Effects of corner type and bagging method on part thickness

Fig. 14 shows the effect of corner type on the thickness measurements for each bagging type. The thicknesses are expressed as a percent increase compared to at section measurements in Fig. 15. These measurements show that in both the flat sections, and outside corners, the thickness of both the Stretchlon bag and silicone bag is quite close to what was predicted, although the parts made using the Stretchlon bag were slightly thicker than those made with the silicone bag. The standard deviation of thickness in both the flat sections and outside corners is not significantly affected by bagging type. The standard deviation was slightly higher in outside corners than in the flat section, which can be attributed to wrinkles forming in the preform.

The thickness measured in the inside corners, and the standard deviation of thickness was significantly higher in the inside corners for parts made using both the Stretchlon bag and silicone bag when compared to the measurements taken in the flat section. The parts made using the silicone bag displayed less thickness increase, and less variation in thickness than those made using the Stretchlon bagging system.

5.2.3 Effects of corner radius on part thickness

Fig. 16 shows the average and standard deviation of thickness for the four different corner radii. Corners between 1.6 mm and 6.4 mm had similar standard deviations and average thicknesses, although a decreasing trend was observed with corner radius. The 12.7 mm corners, however, had an average thickness that was equal to the theoretically predicted flat-panel thickness. The 12.7 mm corners also had a standard deviation of 0.135 mm, which is less than the at section standard deviation of 0.146 mm. This implies that the thickness of the part in the 12.7 mm corner was not affected by the presence of the corner.

5.3 Corner defects in test parts

The presence of void defects in each part was quantified using the method described below, and the effects of corner type, bagging type, and corner radius are presented.

5.3.1 Measurement method

When quantifying the part defects, the presence of a corner void visible to the naked eye, regardless of its size, was recorded. To quantify the corner defects produced by each method, the fraction of parts containing a corner surface void of any size was calculated.

5.3.2 Effects of corner type on part void content

The fraction of parts containing a corner void is shown in Fig. 17 for different corner types and bagging methods. Parts containing outside corners had the lowest chance of containing a corner void, and this was not dependent on the bagging method. A much higher fraction of parts containing inside corners were found to contain corner voids. Of the inside corner parts, those made using the silicone bag had a much higher chance of containing a corner void than those made using the Stretchlon bagging method.

Even though the silicone bag was able to provide more compaction pressure in the inside corners, a higher fraction of parts made using this method contained a void. This suggests that compaction pressure is not the most significant factor when determining void content. This discrepancy could have been caused by a poor seal between the silicone bag and the mould. The silicone bag was sealed by placing the tacky tape outside the bag to mimic the method used on the GeoSurv II fuselage, and this method does not provide as good a seal as the traditional method of placing the tacky tape underneath the bag. If more air was able to enter the bag and become trapped in the corners, this could have led to the higher void content seen in the parts made with the silicone bag.

5.3.3 Effects of corner radius on part void content

Fig. 18 shows the fraction of parts of the four different radii that contained a corner void. Parts containing a smaller radius were much more likely to contain a corner void, with the most significant decrease taking place between 1.6 mm and 3.2 mm. The 12.7 mm radius corners had the lowest likelihood of containing a corner void, at 18%.

6 Conclusions

Loss of compaction pressure was proposed as a possible cause of the thickness variations and void content commonly found in parts made using a VARTM infusion. The compaction pressure was experimentally measured in various locations in preforms containing complex, three-dimensional shapes, and found to decrease by as much as 68% in inside corners, suggesting that compaction pressure loss is a significant cause of manufacturing defects. A compaction pressure loss of 61% was predicted using a theoretical approach, suggesting that bag tension is a significant factor in corner defect formation

The effects of the presence of a corner on part thickness, and corner voids were studied for two different bagging techniques. The radius of the corner was found to have a significant effect on thickness variations and corner voids. By far the greatest increase in performance occurred in the 12.7 mm radius specimens. However, it will not always be feasible to incorporate such a large radius into all composite designs, and significant improvements in compaction pressure, void content, and strength were present in radii 3.2 mm and larger.

Parts manufactured using the silicone bag tended to have better compaction and have less variability than those made using the Stretchlon bag and pressure enhancers. However, parts manufactured using the Stretchlon bagging technique had a much lower likelihood of containing voids in the vicinity of the corner. This was attributed to the ability of the Stretchlon bag to form a better seal against the mould surface, allowing less air to enter the cavity.

Based on these experiments, the silicone bagging technique will, in general, produce parts with higher strength and tighter tolerances. However, this technique tends to lead to voids in small part details, so if a high-quality surface finish free of voids is required, the Stretchlon bagging technique with pressure enhancers is a more appropriate solution.

Based on the void measurements, outside corners contained relatively few voids whereas inside corners contained more. The Stretchlon bag with pressure enhancers reduced the presence of voids compared to silicone. Corner radii of 3.2 mm or greater greatly decreased the chance of corner voids forming.

The experimental results can be used to optimize part design to minimize defects in the VARTM

A STUDY OF THE QUALITY OF COMPLEX PARTS MADE USING THE MOULDLESS VARTM METHOD

process. For example, if parts with minimal thickness variations are required, a silicone bag with a 12.7 mm minimum inside corner radius should be used. If parts with minimal void content are desired, a Stretchlon bag with pressure enhancers, and a minimum inside corner radius of 3.2 mm should be used.

Fig. 1. GeoSurv II UAV

Fig. 2. The mouldless VARTM process

Fig. 3. Corner void defect in the GeoSurv II fuselage

Fig. 4. Corner defect creation due to bag tension

Fig. 5. Corner defect creation due to bridging

Fig. 6. Corner defect creation due to fibre wrinkling

Fig. 7. Sum of forces acting on vacuum bag in part corners

Fig. 8. GeoSurv II fuselage during infusion

Fig. 9. Instrumentation of fuselage vacuum bag

Fig. 10. Pressure sensor reading during infusion

A STUDY OF THE QUALITY OF COMPLEX PARTS MADE USING THE MOULDLESS VARTM METHOD

Fig. 11. Corner test part dimensions

Fig. 13. Corner test part manufacturing

Fig. 12. Placement of pressure enhancers in layup

Fig. 14. Average part thickness with corner type and bagging technique

Fig. 15. Percent change of part thickness with corner type and bagging technique

Fig. 16. Average part thickness with corner radius. Error bars show one standard deviation

Fig. 17. Effects of corner type and bagging technique on corner defects

Fig. 18. Effects of corner radius on corner defects

References

- [1] J. Maley, "An Investigation Into Low-Cost Manufacturing of Carbon Epoxy Composites and a Novel "Mouldless" Technique Using the VARTM Method". MASc Thesis, MAAE Department, Carleton University, 2008.
- [2] M. Mahendran, "An Improved Mouldless Manufacturing Method For Foam-Core Composite Sandwich Structures". MASc Thesis, MAAE Department, Carleton University, 2010.
- [3] J. O'Flynn. *Design for Manufacturability of a Composite Helicopter Structure Made by Resin Transfer Moulding*. Master's thesis, McGill University, November 2007.
- [4] SP-High Modulus, Vacuum Consumables.
- [5] J. M. Lawrence, K. T. Hsiao, R. C. Don, P.I Simacek, G. Estrada, E. M. Sozer, H. C. Stadtfeld, and S. G. Advani. An Approach to Couple Mold Design and On-Line Control to Manufacture Complex Composite Parts by Resin Transfer Molding. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 33(7):981-990, July 2002.
- [6] X. Song, A. C. Loos, B. W. Grimsley, R. J. Cano, and P. Hubert. Modeling the VARTM Composite Manufacturing Process. *4th SAMPE International Symposium*, 20(1), 2004.
- [7] J. Li. *Modeling, Design and Control of Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) for Thickness Variation Reduction*. PhD thesis, Florida State University, 2006.
- [8] Correia, N. C., Robitaille, F., Long, a. C., Rudd, C. D., Simacek, P., & Advani, S. G. "Use of Resin Transfer Molding Simulation to Predict Flow, Saturation, and Compaction in the VARTM Process". *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, Vol. 126, No. 2, pp 210-215, 2004.
- [9] DuPont. DuPont Hytrel TPC-ET Thermoplastic Polyester Elastomer. http://www2.dupont.com/Plastics/enn_US/Products/Hytrel/Hytrel.html.
- [10] D. Evans P. Evans. Patent for a Vacuum Bagging Apparatus and Method Including a Thermoplastic Elastomer Film Vacuum Bag. <http://www.patentlens.net/patentlens/patent/USn5123985/>, June 1992.
- [11] Interlink Electronics. FSR 400. <http://www.interlinkelectronics.com/FSR400.php>.
- [12] Composites Canada. Stretchlon Bagging Film SL-200. <http://www.compositescanada.com/product.php?idProduct=309>.